

The influence of geopolitics on research activity and international collaboration in science: The case of Russia

Lin Zhang¹, Zhe Cao², Gunnar Sivertsen³

¹ linzhang1117@whu.edu.cn

Center for Science, Technology & Education Assessment (CSTEA), Wuhan University, Wuhan (China)
School of Information Management, Wuhan University, Wuhan (China)
Centre for R&D Monitoring (ECOOM) and Department of MSI, KU Leuven, Leuven (Belgium)

² caozhe@whu.edu.cn

Center for Science, Technology & Education Assessment (CSTEA), Wuhan University, Wuhan (China)
School of Information Management, Wuhan University, Wuhan (China)

³ gunnar.sivertsen@nifu.no

Nordic Institute for Studies in Innovation, Research and Education (NIFU), Oslo (Norway)

Abstract

We study the possible influences of Russia's invasion of Ukraine in February 2022 on the country's research productivity, thematic profile, and international collaboration in science. For the analysis of the latter, we introduce and apply two recently developed indicators of relative intensity and balance in international collaboration. To see whether longitudinal trends have changed recently, we combine a long-term perspective based on annual updates since the year 2000 with a short-term perspective based on monthly updates since the beginning of 2022. We find that the trends in Russia's pattern of international collaboration have not changed much after February 2022 except for in fields of research based on costly multinational infrastructures. The clearest change is that the productivity of Russian science, as measured within Web of Science, has recently decreased after several years of growth. The downward trend is seen in both domestic and internationally co-authored articles. It seems that the invasion of Ukraine has mainly influenced science within Russia in a negative way while the country's international relations in science remain more stable.

Introduction

In recent years, there have seen increasing tensions between science policies advocating openness and globalization on the one hand, and foreign policies much more focused on competition, trade sanctions, self-containment, and security and defence on the other. Taking the latter perspective of foreign policies, the present pattern of global collaboration in science represents a paradox. It does not follow the borders of defence alliances. The highest relative collaboration intensity of the United States (hereafter "the US") is with Canada, South Korea, and China according to the bibliometric indicator of 'Relative international collaboration specialization' in the *Science & Engineering Indicators* report published by the US' *National Science Foundation* (2021). Of these three countries, only Canada is an ally of the US. China is by far the largest collaboration partner of the US in terms of the total of co-authored papers despite the political tensions between the two countries in recent years. According to a study of global collaboration intensities in science (Sivertsen, 2022), the intensity in the relations between member countries of NATO in northern Europe is higher with Russia than with the US.

The situation after the Russian invasion of Ukraine on February 24, 2022, presents us with a similar contradiction between collaboration in science and political conflicts. Politically, Russia quickly became the most sanctioned nation in the world (Zandt, 2022) with no exception for governmental agreements and investments in science and technology, but the international scientific communities themselves have been more hesitant to stop collaboration. At the

governmental level, the US's White House Office of Science and Technology Policy has decided to “wind down” government-to-government research collaboration with Russia and no longer start new projects (The White House, 2022). The German government has officially suspended all governmental cooperation with Russia in science and asked other European countries to follow suit (Plackett, 2022). As a typical example, the publicly funded German Electron Synchrotron Center (DESY) has suspended all organizational-level collaboration, including visits, conferences, and co-publishing, with similar institutions in Russia and Belarussia. However, it has been decided to keep contacts with scientists on an individual basis, thereby reflecting the long-standing consensus in scientific communities worldwide that science should have no borders. Along with a strong condemnation of Russia and an explicit sympathy with Ukraine in an editorial on March 4, (Nature, 2022) at the same time supported the plea of the InterAcademy Partnership (IAP, the main global alliance of academies of science) to “leave no one behind” in global science collaboration and said the journal would “continue to consider manuscripts from researchers anywhere in the world”. According to *Science* a few days later on March 10, editors and publishers of scientific journals had largely refused the call of Ukrainian scientists to decline publishing manuscripts from Russian scientists (Brainard, 2022). The resistance of global scientific communities towards being steered by geopolitical conflicts seems to prevail even under high pressure.

There are recent cases where geopolitics have been demonstrated to influence international collaboration patterns to some degree. The relative intensity of collaboration between the US and China has been declining since it peaked in 2016 while the opposite is the case for the relation between the UK and China (Rousseau, Zhang, & Sivertsen, 2023). The decrease in relative collaboration intensity between the US and China is therefore not explained by the COVID-19 travel restrictions, but most probably by the deteriorating relations between the two countries since 2018 (Tang et al., 2021; Zweig, 2021). However, we have not observed dramatic changes so far.

Based on the general picture presented above with global collaboration patterns that might seem paradoxical from a geopolitical point of view, our hypothesis is that the Russian invasion of Ukraine has not considerably affected the long-term patterns and trends in international scientific collaboration. We will test this hypothesis by using partly new methods. For the analysis of international collaboration, we apply a recently developed refinement of the measurement of collaboration intensity (Fuchs, Sivertsen, & Rousseau, 2021) along with a new indicator that measures the balance in the collaboration profile of a country over time (Rousseau, Zhang, & Sivertsen, 2023). We extend the collaboration analysis with an analysis of possible changes in productivity and the thematic profile of Russian science, as well as the publications in internationally indexed Russian journals.

Data and methods

To test our hypothesis about the relative stability in Russia's collaboration and publication patterns, we combine a long-term perspective with an analysis of annual changes since the year 2000 and a short-term perspective with an analysis of monthly changes since the beginning of the year 2022. For the former, data from 2000 to the present were downloaded from InCites Benchmarking & Analytics™ (hereinafter “InCites”), a platform launched by Clarivate, offering indicators built upon the publications metadata in the Web of Science™ Core Collection (hereinafter “WoS”)¹. For the latter, data from 2021 to the present were retrieved

¹ <https://clarivate.com/webofsciencigroup/solutions/incites/>

from WoS, with 2021 data serving as a reference. The document type adopted in our study is *Article*. With publication date² provided in the *full record*, finer-grained timing analysis, namely analysis based on month-to-month publication data could be conducted.

For the collaboration analysis, we introduced two newly proposed indicators to our study. To measure the collaborative activity between Russia and other countries, relative intensity of collaboration (*RIC*) was used (Fuchs, Sivertsen, & Rousseau, 2021), which compares the share of country *Y* within the collaboration profile of country *X* to the share of *Y* within all collaborations in the whole network, which is calculated as:

$$RIC(X, Y) := \frac{\frac{C_{XY}}{C_X}}{\frac{C_Y - C_{XY}}{T - C_X}} = \frac{C_{XY} \cdot (T - C_X)}{C_X \cdot (C_Y - C_{XY})}$$

where C_{XY} denotes the number of collaborations between countries *X* and *Y*; C_X (C_Y) denotes the total number of collaborations country *X* (*Y*) has with all other countries; and *T* denotes the total number of pairwise country collaborations in the set of publications under study.

Another indicator, balance in collaboration (*BIC*) is used to evaluate the balance of Russia's international collaboration. *BIC* is based on the Gini evenness index for a weighted Lorenz curve (Rousseau, Zhang, & Sivertsen, 2023), represented as:

$$BIC(X, Y) = \sum_{j=k+1}^N (b_j + b_{j-1})w_j, \text{ where } b_j = 1 - \sum_{m=1}^j a_m, j = 1, \dots, N \text{ and } b_0 = 1$$

In the formula, $w_j = \frac{C_Y - C_{XY}}{2(T - C_X)}$ and $a_m = \frac{C_{XY}}{C_X}$. *BIC* can be regarded as an extension for the use of *RIC*.

The calculation of the two indicators is further explained in Fuchs et al. (2021) and in Rousseau et al. (2023). It should be noted that when calculating these two indicators, we only consider the 20 most productive countries in terms of scientific articles according to the 2021 ranking of InCites. Articles with contributions by researchers from these countries represented 88.3% of all international collaborative articles published in that year.

In terms of the thematic profile, we apply a document-level classification schema, Citation Topics, which was developed with the expertise of the CWTS in Leiden and the Institute for Scientific Information (Potter, 2020). This schema includes three levels of topics – 10 macro-topics, 326 meso-topics and 2444 micro-topics. We mainly focus on macro and meso levels to detect possible major changes. In this analysis we separate between international collaborated articles (ICA) and articles with domestic authors only (non-ICA) to control for the influence of country relations. We further differentiate between bilateral collaboration and multilateral collaboration since the two types of collaborations may be influenced in different ways by geopolitics.

To study possible changes in productivity and thematic profile, we use two datasets, Russian

² The publication month is extracted from the publication date, which has five writing forms: (1) month day (e.g. JAN 1); (2) month (e.g. JAN); (3) month₁-month₂ (e.g. JAN-FEB); (4) season (e.g. SPR); (5) season₁-season₂ (e.g. SPR-FALL). The former two cases are normal. For (3), we used month₁ as the publication month. Cases (4) and (5) are excluded from our analysis, since these cases only account for around 1% in the dataset.

articles indexed in WoS and articles published in Russian journals that are indexed in WoS. For the latter, we selected 390 journals published by Russian institutions according to 2021 Journal Citation Reports (JCR)³, and downloaded the *full record* of all articles published in these journals from 2021 to the present (the 2021 data is for comparison). Figure 1 demonstrates the framework of data processing and analysis.

Figure 1. Framework of data processing and analysis

Results

Russia's international collaboration

The analysis of international collaboration is limited to the twenty largest science producing countries among which Russia ranks number sixteen by contributing to 2 percent of the world's scientific articles. Over the past two decades, Germany has been the largest collaborator of Russia in general, producing 67,030 collaborated articles in total, followed by the US, France, the UK, Italy and China. The number of collaborated articles from Russia and each of the 19 productive countries shows a growing trend, but there has been growth in all bilateral relations during the two decades (Sivertsen, 2022). Hence, it is more interesting to look at the relative intensity of collaboration.

There are large variations in the collaborative intensity in Russia's relations to the other countries. The preference of Russia towards Poland and Germany in research collaboration is most prominent, with a *RIC* value of 2.20 and 1.71 respectively, whereas the intensity with Canada and Australia is low with a *RIC* value of 0.59 and 0.53 respectively.

Over the years, the *RIC* between Russia and Germany, and Russia and the US, has continuously declined while it has increased in relation to the Asian countries including China, India, Turkey and Iran. There is also an increasing trend for Australia. Among other European countries, declining intensity is not observed in the relations to France and the UK, but the relationship with Netherlands and Sweden weakened more before 2014, the year of Russia's annexation of Crimea, while the relations to Poland and Switzerland declined since that year. To conclude, a

³ <https://jcr.clarivate.com/jcr/home>

Russian shift toward the East in scientific collaboration can be observed from a long-term perspective.

Table 1. Collaborations between Russia and 19 countries during 2000-2022

No.	Partner C	Total number of collaborated articles	Annual number of collaborated articles	RIC(Russia, C)	Trends of RIC values
1	Germany	67030			
2	US	66597			
3	France	38483			
4	UK	34240			
5	Italy	27798			
6	China	24740			
7	Japan	20128			
8	Spain	19631			
9	Poland	18568			
10	Switzerland	16461			
11	Netherlands	15610			
12	Sweden	14807			
13	Canada	13770			
14	India	11675			
15	South Korea	11425			
16	Australia	10587			
17	Brazil	10399			
18	Turkey	7256			
19	Iran	3982			

To investigate possible changes after Russia's invasion of Ukraine in February, 2022, we conducted a monthly analysis of relative collaboration intensity. As observed in Figure 2, the long-term trends found above have not changed much. The collaboration intensity in the relations to China, India and Turkey continues to increase whereas it is clearly decreasing in the relation to Poland and there are signs of decline in the relations to Germany and the UK. Notably, there are no signs of decline in the relation to the US the past few months. We conclude that the invasion of Ukraine so far has not affected Russia's international collaboration pattern dramatically except for in the relations to European neighbouring countries.

Figure 1. Monthly trends of RIC between Russia and 8 representative countries

The long-term turn towards the East in Russia’s scientific relations has not changed the balance in the country’s collaboration pattern, as seen in Figure 3, but the balance was slightly distorted most recently, indicating that Russia is now becoming more dependent on collaboration with Turkey, India, and China (see also Figure 2). Apart from this, the new indicator of balance that we apply here shows clear increases for China and the US in the most recent five years which are mainly due to the ‘internal’ decrease in the relative collaboration intensity between the two largest and still very close scientific collaboration partners in the world.

Figure 2. Annual and monthly trends of BIC of Russia and four other countries

Russia’s thematic research profile

For an overview of possible changes in the thematic research profile of Russia, the distribution and evolution of macro topics from 2000 to 2022 is presented in Figure 4. The most eye-catching observation is the difference between the thematic profiles of articles with and without international collaboration (ICA and non-ICA). *Chemistry* dominates non-ICA with a share of around 30% in the past two decades, while *Physics* is the most active field of Russia’s international collaborations despite a dramatic decline of relative shares. Compared with non-

ICA, the topical distribution of ICA from Russia is much more uneven in general, with *Physics*, *Chemistry* and *Clinical & Life Sciences* as the most dominant fields. However, the field distribution has become much more balanced during the past 10 years.

Figure 3. Distribution of macro topics of non-ICA and ICA from Russia within years 2000-2022

In order to see whether there is a recent impact of geopolitics on particular research fields, we further zoom into the thematic profiles of Russia’s ICA published after 2021. Figure 5 shows the monthly trend of the proportions of articles on 10 macro topics of bilateral and multilateral collaborations respectively. The trends within selected representative meso-level topics are demonstrated as examples.

The first notable observation is the clear decline of both bilateral and multilateral international collaborated articles since the beginning of 2022. We will return to this observation below. The second observation is that the research profile has slightly changed at the same time. The dominant role of *Physics* seems to be weakened during the most recent months, in particular, the meso-topic of *Particles & Fields* and *Astronomy & Astrophysics* in the multilateral collaborations. These fields of research are traditionally important in Russia with its predominantly “physics and technology” profile with origins in the Soviet period (Sokolov et al., 2018). They have been important in the Nuclear Arms Race and the Space Race, and they continue to be important from a security and defense perspective. Today, both research fields are partly supported by large globally shared infrastructures organized by consortia in which Russia is one of many member countries or has been welcomed to participate. These consortia involve large-scale governmental investments. An example of withdrawal from formal collaboration with Russia and Belarussia, the national particle physics infrastructure DESY in Germany, was given in the introduction. The decrease of large infrastructure-demanding research in Russia’s research profile might be an effect of it being expelled from formal participation in such infrastructures abroad.

Figure 4. Monthly distribution of articles in 10 macro topics and 6 representative meso topics

Russia's scientific production in international journals

As observed in the subplot on the top of Figure 6, the first ten years of the 21st century has witnessed a transitional period after the collapse of the Soviet Union. While the total number of articles decreased at first and then started to rise, the number of articles with international collaboration (ICA) did not fluctuate much. Over the last decade, the number of Russian articles and the share of ICA have steadily increased. The bottom of Figure 6 zooms into the monthly development in 2021-2022. The scientific production of Russia in international journals decreases, most clearly after April 2022 and in comparison with the same months in the previous year. The proportion of Russia's ICA also slowly declines. To investigate whether these declines are also due to local conditions, our last analysis is focused on Russian journals.

Figure 5. Annual and monthly trends of the number of articles from Russia and the ICA rate

Articles in Russian journals

Among the over 21,000 journals in Clarivate’s Journal Citation Report, there are 390 journals published by Russian institutions. They published a total number of 39,050 articles in 2021-2022, accounting for approximately forty percent of all 96,024 articles with Russian affiliations indexed in WoS during this period. Within the 390 journals, around 79 percent of the articles have Russian affiliations (but may also have foreign co-authors). These journals may provide a closer look at what is happening in Russian science.

Figure 7 shows the monthly trend in the number of articles published in the WoS-indexed Russian journals during 2021-2022. Here, the language used in the journal is also taken into consideration as well as whether the Russian institution responsible for the journal makes use of a domestic or foreign publisher to distribute the journal. The overall number of articles published in the journals has clearly been decreasing since March 2022, but with no indication of general change in language and type of publisher.

Figure 6. Monthly trends of the number of articles published on Russian journals and the distribution of languages and publishers

Discussion and conclusion

Our results confirm our hypothesis that geopolitical conflicts only marginally affect long-term patterns and trends in international scientific collaboration. Russian science is to a high degree integrated in global science, and the relative intensity of collaboration in bilateral relations remains relatively stable. This stability is mainly provided in the relations to the two largest science-producing countries where we observe stability in the relation to the US and increase in the relation to China. Increases can be observed also in the relations to India and Turkey, while decreases are observed in relations to European countries such as Poland, Germany and the UK, and in fields of research demanding large international infrastructures that are sensitive from a security and defence perspective. There are also signs that the degree of international collaboration is decreasing in scientific articles from Russia, and that the output of Russian journals is decreasing.

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References

- Brainard, J. (2022). Few journals heed calls to boycott Russian papers. *Science*, 10 March.
- Fuchs, J. E., Sivertsen, G., & Rousseau, R. (2021). Measuring the relative intensity of collaboration within a network. *Scientometrics*, 126(10), 8673-8682. doi:10.1007/s11192-021-04110-x
- National Science Foundation. (2021). *Science & Engineering Indicators. Publications Output: U.S. Trends and International Comparisons*. Retrieved from <https://ncses.nsf.gov/pubs/nsb20214>
- Nature. (2022). Russia's brutal attack on Ukraine is wrong and must stop. Editorial. *Nature*, 4 March, doi:10.1038/d41586-022-00647-w
- Plackett, B. (2022). The future of research collaborations involving Russia. *Nature*, 18 March.
- Potter, I. (2020). *Introducing Citation Topics in InCites*. Retrieved from <https://clarivate.com/blog/introducing-citation-topics/>

- Rousseau, R., Zhang, L., & Sivertsen, G. (2023). Using the weighted Lorenz curve to represent balance in collaborations: the BIC indicator. *Scientometrics*, 128(1), 609-622. doi:10.1007/s11192-022-04533-0
- Sivertsen, G. (2022). Norway's scientific collaboration with China in a global context: An analysis based on articles in Web of Science. *NIFU Working Paper 2022:1*. <https://nifu.brage.unit.no/nifu-xmlui/handle/11250/2983834>
- Sokolov, A., Shashnov, S., Kotsemir, M., et al. (2018). S&T Priorities for BRICS Countries: In Search of a Win-Win Strategy. In X. Zhao, M. Li, M. Huang, & A. Sokolov (Eds.), *BRICS Innovative Competitiveness Report 2017* (pp. 31-65). Singapore: Springer Singapore.
- Tang, L., Cao, C., Wang, Z., et al. (2021). Decoupling in science and education: A collateral damage beyond deteriorating US–China relations. *Science and Public Policy*, 48(5), 630-634. doi:10.1093/scipol/scab035
- The White House (2022). *Guidance on Scientific and Technological Cooperation with the Russian Federation for U.S. Government and U.S. Government Affiliated Organizations*. Retrieved from <https://www.whitehouse.gov/ostp/news-updates/2022/06/11/guidance-on-scientific-and-technological-cooperation-with-the-russian-federation-for-u-s-government-and-u-s-government-affiliated-organizations/>
- Zandt, F. (2022). *The World's Most-Sanctioned Countries*. Retrieved from <https://www.statista.com/chart/27015/number-of-currently-active-sanctions-by-target-country/>
- Zweig, D. S. (2021). Is Sino–American Scientific Collaboration a Thing of the Past? *International Higher Education*, (108), 5-7.